

CENTRAL REFLECTION AND ITS USE IN FORMULATION OF UNIT CELLS FOR MICROMECHANICAL FEA

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1 Introduction

Symmetry as a geometric property is a well understood topic. There are three generic types of symmetries: translations, reflections and rotations. All of them have been used to different extents in structural analyses, with reflections being most attended to such an extent that they are sometimes perceived as the symmetry, as transpired through the fact that it is the only type of symmetries that has been incorporated in most commercial FE codes. To implement other types, such as translations and rotations, the user will have to improvise using the facility of equation boundary conditions or multiple point constraints.

The three generic types of symmetries have also been utilised extensively in formulating unit cells for micromechanical analyses of materials of regular microstructures [1-7]. Of them, translations result in the commonly called periodic conditions. The benefits of using translational symmetries alone have been elaborated in reasonable length in [2,3,4,6] that a single set of boundary conditions applies for any loading condition in terms of a single macroscopic stress component or a combination of several of them. The existence of further symmetries, such as reflections and rotations, can be used to reduce the size of the unit cell, as has been illustrated in analyses of UD composites [1,4] and more recently plain weave textile composites [5]. However, the use of reflectional and rotational symmetries tends to restrict the applicability in terms of combined loading conditions. Also, different sets of boundary conditions have to be imposed when the unit cell is under different loading conditions. While a single set of boundary conditions offers conveniences, reduced unit cell size is computationally attractive, especially when dealing with complicated unit cells, e.g. for textile composites where high demand on computing power often arises [6]. A compromise has not been available.

Mathematically, these three types of symmetries are mutually independent and collectively comprehensive so that any other type of symmetry, such reflection about the central point, etc., can be obtained as a simple combination of some of these generic symmetries and is hence not independent. The lack of independence of such derived symmetries has probably deterred users from exploiting them. As a result, they have never been employed in structural analyses.

A central reflection is a combination of a plane reflection and a 180° rotation. Taking advantage of this when it is available in a unit cell, it will produce a set of boundary conditions which is applicable to all loading cases as well any combination of macroscopic stresses, while halving the size of the unit cell. Neither a plane reflection nor a rotation alone delivers such a property.

2 Central reflection

Mechanical applications of geometric symmetries are complicated by the existence of two different natures, *viz.* symmetry and anti-symmetry, which are related to applied loads, as well as the internal stresses and strains, in presence of geometric symmetry. Loading conditions for micromechanical analyses of unit cells are typically expressed in terms of macroscopic stresses or strains. They preserve symmetric nature under translational symmetry transformations. This is responsible for the fact that a single set of boundary conditions are applicable for all loading conditions if only translational symmetries are used.

Reflectional and rotational symmetries only preserve the senses of some stress and strain components, typically those direct stresses, but not others, typically some shear stresses and strains, for which the concept of antisymmetry has to be resorted to. Involvement of any of these symmetries splits applied loads, as well as stresses and strains,

into two mutually exclusive categories, symmetric and antisymmetric. As a result, different boundary conditions will have to be prescribed under different loading conditions. This prohibits any combination of loads of different natures, undermining the use of reflectional and rotational symmetries. Unit cell users have been left in a dilemma in which one can have either a full sized unit cell under a single set of boundary conditions for all loading conditions or a unit cell with reduced size, which has to be analysed using separate sets of boundary conditions under different loading conditions, stripping its capability of dealing with combined loading conditions.

A centrally reflectional symmetry (CR) is often observed in popular objects. However, patterns and shapes possessing this symmetry often show other symmetries, such as reflections and rotations, making the recognition of CR either redundant or unobvious. A simple but distinctive shape of CR is a triclinic crystal, Fig. 1, which is a hexahedron of three parallel, unnecessarily orthogonal, pairs of faces and three independent side lengths. In this geometry, CR is the only symmetry available.

Fig. 1 A triclinic crystal

The analytical description of CR can be given as a mapping

$$CR: P \rightarrow P' \quad (1)$$

where $P(x, y, z)$ is an arbitrary point in the triclinic body as origin and $P'(x', y', z')$ as the image of P , or

$$(x' - x_0, y' - y_0, z' - z_0) = -(x - x_0, y - y_0, z - z_0) \quad (2)$$

(x_0, y_0, z_0) being the coordinates of the centre O . All stresses and strains preserve their senses under a CR, see Fig. 2, where CR would not cause any change and the same applies to the outward normals to the cube, also shown in Fig. 2. With the outward normals, surface traction can be obtained as a part of the periodic boundary conditions, although they are not required in conventional FE analyses [7]. CR breaks the aforementioned dilemma straightaway, i.e. the size of the unit cell having such symmetry can now be halved without any penalty and the new unit cell of reduced size will come with a single set

of boundary conditions which are applicable to all loading conditions and any of their combinations.

Fig. 2 Stresses showing perfect symmetry under CR

The mapping for displacements is

$$CR: (u - u_0, v - v_0, w - w_0) \rightarrow -(u' - u_0, v' - v_0, w' - w_0) \quad (3)$$

where (u, v, w) and (u', v', w') are the displacements at P and P' , respectively, and (u_0, v_0, w_0) those at O .

This should be dealt with properly and made use of correctly in order to obtain boundary conditions rationally since boundary conditions for unit cells have to be described in terms of displacements.

Consider the application of CR in structural analysis. The triclinic crystal as shown in Fig. 1 has been taken as a symbolic representation of CR structure loaded in a symmetric manner under the same symmetry, Fig. 3(a). Applying the symmetry, the structure can be analysed with only half of it, Fig. 3(b), if appropriate boundary conditions are imposed on the shaded section plane.

Fig. 3 Application of reflectional symmetry

(a) A centrally symmetric structure (b) The symmetric half of the structure

Since relative displacements (to point O) are all centrally reflected to opposite directions according to the symmetry transformation (5), one has

$$\begin{aligned} u - u_0 &= -(u' - u_0) & \text{or} & & u + u' &= 2u_0 \\ v - v_0 &= -(v' - v_0) & & & v + v' &= 2v_0 \\ w - w_0 &= -(w' - w_0) & & & w + w' &= 2w_0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where (u, v, w) and (u', v', w') are displacements at P and P' on the section surface as origin and image under the symmetry transformation. (4) above deliver the desirable boundary conditions for the section surface, when P takes positions of all points on any half of the section plane, e.g. the half on the left hand side of the dash-dot chain in Fig. 3(b). (4) are based on the relative displacements to point O .

This leaves the displacements at O completely free as far as the symmetry is concerned, which accommodate the rigid body translations of the structure. To facilitate an FE analysis, they need to be constrained. To achieve this, they can be prescribed to any fixed values. Without losing generality, one can prescribe

$$u_o = 0, \quad v_o = 0 \quad \& \quad w_o = 0 \quad (5)$$

A proper FE analysis will also require the rigid body rotations constrained. For unit cells, it can be done in a convenient manner [2,3].

The selection of the section plane is not unique. It can be any surface, flat or curved, as long as it is CR symmetric about centre O . Necessarily, it must pass the centre O . The boundary conditions as obtained in (4) and (5) are generally applicable whichever section plane or surface is chosen. They provide the boundary conditions if the structure is to be analysed with a half sized model.

3 Unit cells from periodic conditions and reduced sizes using central reflection

Many unit cells (UCs) of various shapes and capacities have been generated over the years. In many cases, seemingly rather different UCs can actually be unified into a single account [1,4], where the use of translational symmetries has been advocated. At least, translational symmetries should precede the use of any other types of symmetries in any case if one wishes to formulate a UC in a rational manner. Use a reflection or rotation prior to translations is deemed to lead to confusion.

After using translations symmetries, the displacements on paired faces of the UC are found in the following form, in general.

$$u' - u = (x' - x)\epsilon_x^0 + (y' - y)\gamma_{xy}^0 + (z' - z)\gamma_{xz}^0 \quad (6)$$

$$v' - v = (y' - y)\epsilon_y^0 + (z' - z)\gamma_{yz}^0$$

$$w' - w = (z' - z)\epsilon_z^0$$

where (u', v', w') and (u, v, w) are displacements at corresponding points (x', y', z') and (x, y, z) on the opposite faces of the UC, respectively, and $(\epsilon_x^0, \epsilon_y^0, \epsilon_z^0, \gamma_{xy}^0, \gamma_{yz}^0, \gamma_{xz}^0, \gamma_{yx}^0)$ are macroscopic strains. They lead to the so-called periodic boundary conditions for UCs, in general. For a given geometry of the UC, $(x' - x)$, $(y' - y)$ and $(z' - z)$ are usually of constant values for a given pair of faces. Detailed expressions for a range of UCs can be found in [2-3].

Considerations will be now made to those UCs formulated in [2,3], i.e. by using translational

symmetries alone, which also possess a further centrally reflectional symmetry. As a result, the size of these UCs can be halved.

In terms of size reduction of the UCs shown in Fig. 4, using a plane reflectional symmetry would achieve the same effects. However the UCs of reduced size obtained using the plane reflection will have different boundary conditions under different loading conditions while the one obtained using the central reflection will be subject to a single set of boundary conditions under all loading conditions and arbitrary combinations of them.

In order to derive the boundary conditions for the faces in the new half sized UC, the faces or parts of the faces present on the new cell are classified into three mutually exclusive types.

Type I: The newly created face which partitions the full size cell into two halves. An example is the bottom surface as shown in Fig. 4(a). CR maps a half of this face to the other half. This leads the required boundary conditions for this type of face, as given in (4) and (5).

Type II: Faces whose origins under both translational and centrally reflectional symmetry transformations are on the other half. An example is the top surface as shown in Fig. 4(a) in the case of a square UC. It can be established that half of such a face as the image of the other half of the same face under the symmetry transformation of a combination of a translation and the central reflection. The required boundary conditions for this type of faces will result from such relationship between the two halves of the face

$$u' + u = (x'' - x)\epsilon_x^0 + (y'' - y)\gamma_{xy}^0 + (z'' - z)\gamma_{xz}^0 \quad (7)$$

$$v' + v = (y'' - y)\epsilon_y^0 + (z'' - z)\gamma_{yz}^0$$

$$w' + w = (z'' - z)\epsilon_z^0$$

where (u', v', w') and (u, v, w) are displacements at corresponding points (x', y', z') and (x, y, z) from different halves of the face. (x'', y'', z'') is on the opposites side and hence the other half of the full size UC as the origin of (x, y, z) under the translational symmetry transformation and that of (x', y', z') under the CR transformation. Points (x', y', z') and (x, y, z) collapse to the same point at the centre of the face, where the boundary conditions are obtained as

$$\begin{aligned}
u &= \frac{1}{2}(x'' - x)\varepsilon_x^0 + \frac{1}{2}(y'' - y)\gamma_{xy}^0 + \frac{1}{2}(z'' - z)\gamma_{xz}^0 \\
v &= \frac{1}{2}(y'' - y)\varepsilon_y^0 + \frac{1}{2}(z'' - z)\gamma_{yz}^0 \\
w &= \frac{1}{2}(z'' - z)\varepsilon_z^0
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Fig. 4 Unit cells halved in size using CR
(a) Square unit cell for UD (b) Hexagonal unit cell for UD (c) Plain weave textile

Type III: Faces whose origin under the CR is on the other half while the origin under translation remains in the same half. Examples are the left and right side surfaces and the front and back surfaces as shown in Fig. 4(a) in the case of a square UC. As the CR maps the face to the half outside of the new UC under consideration, the displacements on these faces are not affected by the CR. The required boundary conditions remains the same as those derived from pure translational considerations.

Conditions for the above three types of faces, after being applied to all faces of the UC, provide a sufficient set of boundary conditions for the UC of reduced size after using CR. However, they are not all necessary because of the presence of edges and

vertices in the UC, where redundant conditions emerge.

4 Boundary conditions for a rectangular prismatic unit cell

Take a rectangular prismatic UC generated from straight translations in three orthogonal directions for example, in which both cases as in Fig. 4(a) and (c) fall. Suppose it is partitioned by a plane perpendicular to the y -axis, without losing generality, as shown in Fig. 5. Face y_1^0 on the left hand side of the bottom surface of the prism is in the partition plane and it is hence Type I. The image of Face y_1^0 under CR is Face y_2^0 , i.e. the right half of the bottom surface.

Fig. 5 A rectangular prismatic unit cell using CR about O
(a) Faces and vertices (b) Edges

Under translational symmetry in the y direction, the origin of the left hand side half of the top surface, Face y_1^+ , is on the missing half of the full size UC and that under CR is also on the missing half. Face y_1^+ is therefore of Type II. Its image under combined y translation and central reflection is Face y_2^+ , i.e. the right hand side half of the top surface.

The origin of Face x^+ under the translational symmetry is Face x^- on the same half of the UC. The origin of Face x^+ under CR is on the missing half of the UC. This pair of faces, Face x^+ and Face x^- , are therefore Type III, so are Face z^+ and Face z^- .

Thus, the boundary conditions between corresponding points on faces (excluding edges):

$$u_{x^+} - u_{x^-} = 2b_x \varepsilon_x^0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_{x^+} - U_{x^-} = F_{\pm x} \tag{9}$$

$$v_{x^+} - v_{x^-} = 0$$

$$w_{x^+} - w_{x^-} = 0$$

$$u_{y_1^+} + u_{y_2^+} = 2b_y \gamma_{xy}^0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_{y_1^+} + U_{y_2^+} = F_{\pm y} \tag{10}$$

$$v_{y_1^+} + v_{y_2^+} = 2b_y \varepsilon_y^0$$

$$w_{y_1^+} + w_{y_2^+} = 0$$

where Face y_1^+ includes the $z<0$ part of the intersection between y_1^+ and y_2^+ on one side of C (excluding C) and Face y_1^+ includes the $z>0$ part of the intersection on the other side of C , as indicated by the dotted frame in Fig. 5(a),

$$u_c = b_y \gamma_{xy}^0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_c = \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm y} \quad (11)$$

$$v_c = b_y \varepsilon_y^0$$

$$w_c = 0$$

$$u_{y_1^0} + u_{y_2^0} = 0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_{y_1^0} + U_{y_2^0} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$v_{y_1^0} + v_{y_2^0} = 0$$

$$w_{y_1^0} + w_{y_2^0} = 0$$

where Face y_1^0 includes the $z<0$ part of the intersection between y_1^0 and y_2^0 on one side of C (excluding C) and Face y_2^0 includes the $z>0$ part of the intersection on the other side of C , as indicated by the dotted frame in Fig. 5(a),

$$u_o = 0, \quad v_o = 0 \quad \& \quad w_o = 0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_o = 0. \quad (13)$$

$$u_{z^+} - u_{z^-} = 2b_z \gamma_{xz}^0 \quad \text{abbr. as } U_{z^+} - U_{z^-} = F_{\pm z} \quad (14)$$

$$v_{z^+} - v_{z^-} = 2b_z \gamma_{yz}^0$$

$$w_{z^+} - w_{z^-} = 2b_z \varepsilon_z^0$$

Between corresponding points on edges, using the abbreviations as introduced above:

$$\vec{U}_{II} - \vec{U}_I = F_{\pm z}$$

$$\vec{U}_{III} - \vec{U}_I = F_{\pm x} + F_{\pm z} \quad (15)$$

$$\vec{U}_{IV} - \vec{U}_I = F_{\pm x}$$

where the arrows on top of U indicate the relative directions in the ordering the nodes along these edges. The similar conditions can be obtained for other edges in similar manner.

For the vertices, conditions can also be obtained as follows for one group of them as an example

$$U_1 = -\frac{1}{2} F_{\pm x} - \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm z} \quad U_3 = -\frac{1}{2} F_{\pm x} + \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm z}$$

$$U_5 = \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm x} + \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm z} \quad U_7 = \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm x} - \frac{1}{2} F_{\pm z} \quad (16)$$

The equation boundary conditions as given above require the mesh for the UC so generated that the nodes and the tessellations on corresponding faces and edges are identically according to the symmetries employed to related the corresponding faces or edges.

5 Examples of applications

Before any serious applications, the new unit cell has passed some sanity checks as suggested in [2,3].

A square and a hexagonal unit cell for UD composites have been analysed in [2] where 2D

meshes were employed by taking advantage of generalised plane strain problem. However, the longitudinal shear had to be analysed separately since the generalised plane strain problem in ABAQUS does not involve this. To avoid separate analyses, 3D brick elements have been employed now. Since there is no stress/strain variation along the fibre direction, a single element in the direction is sufficient. Using the same constituent material properties, identical outcomes to those provided in [3] are obtained.

A simplistic microstructure representing a plain weave textile composite was employed in [5] as an example. The same idealisation has been adapted here in order to illustrate the application of the formulated boundary conditions.

As there have been some typographic errors in the input data in [5], the correct ones have been shown in Table 1. While most part of Table 2 are identical to its counterpart in [5], the effective thermal expansion coefficients as predicted here have been included, which resulted from an extra step of temperature loading analysis. In order to extract all effective elastic properties, six loading cases have to be applied. The analyses in [5] had to be accomplished with four separate analyses with four sets of different boundary conditions. In the present unit cell, a single set of boundary conditions applies to all six loading conditions, as well as the temperature loading, and the job was carried out in a single run.

Table 1 Input properties for the validation cases

	E_1 (GPa)	$E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	α_1 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	$\alpha_2=\alpha_3$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)
Yarn	6.4029	2.8552	1.1533	1.0824	0.2337	8.0815	23.804
Matrix	1	1	0.38462	0.38462	0.3	50	50

Table 2 Effective properties of a plain weave textile

$E_1=E_2$ (GPa)	E_3 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	$G_{13}=G_{23}$ (GPa)	ν_{12}	$\nu_{13}=\nu_{23}$	$\alpha_1=\alpha_2$ ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)	α_3 ($10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$)
3.41	2.21	0.856	0.818	0.163	0.301	8.0815	23.804

composite obtained from the unit cell

A key difference between the unit cell formulated here and that in [5] is that the present unit cell is subjected to a single set of boundary conditions under all loading conditions and any combination of macroscopic stresses can be imposed. As an example, the unit cell is analysed under a combined macroscopic stresses of $\sigma_x^0 = \gamma_{xy}^0 = 1 \text{ MPa}$. Fig. 6

shows the stress contour plots out of this analysis. Such a combined loading condition is prohibited with the unit cell presented in [5].

Fig. 6 stress contour plot of the unit cell under combined macroscopic stresses of $\sigma_x^0 = \gamma_{xy}^0 = 1 \text{ MPa}$

(a) Mises stress in composite (b) σ_1 in yarns (c) σ_2 in yarns (d) τ_{12} in yarns (e) Mises stress in matrix

6 Conclusions

Unit cells taking advantage of centrally reflectional symmetry have been formulated with boundary conditions derived according to this particular

geometric symmetry. While a unit cell so formulated is of half of the size of the unit cell as is conventionally formulated purely based on the periodic conditions, it loses no practical advantages in terms of its applications. Like conventional unit cells obtained purely from periodic conditions, the new unit cells of reduced sizes can be analysed with a single set of boundary conditions for any loading condition or any combined loading condition. It should be noted that central reflection as a type of symmetry has been used in structural analysis for the first time here

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